

ISic1320

I.Sicily inscription 1320

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140814

1. τύμβον □ ὄρα□ς, παροδεΐτα, [πε]ρικλειτῆς
2. Ῥοδογούνης □ | ἦν □ κτάν□εν οὐχ ὀσίως □
3. λάεσι δεινὸς □ ἀνὴρ □ | κλαῦσε δὲ □ καὶ □ τάρ-
4. χυσε □ Ἀβιάνιος □ ἦν □ παράκοιτιν □ | καὶ
5. βαιὴν □ στήλη □ τήνδ' □ ἀπέδωκε □ χάριν. |
6. ὄνομα □ τὸ πρὶν □ με □ πᾶς ἔκκληζεν #⁵⁶
7. □ Ἐπαγαθῶ, □ |
8. νῦν □ δὲ Ῥοδογούνην □ βασιλίδος
9. □ τὸ □ ἐ□πώνυμον. □
- 10.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492926

EDCS 39101691

PHI 140814

Bibliography

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